

9.3: Input for the Interactive Online Map

Spatial Aspects of Deradicalisation

UK.

January 2024

Dr. Maggie Laidlaw Glasgow Caledonian University

© Dr Maggie Laidlaw Glasgow Caledonian University

Reference: D.RAD [D9.3]

ISBN: []

This research was conducted under the Horizon 2020 project 'De-Radicalisation in Europe and Beyond: Detect, Resolve, Re-integrate' (959198).

The sole responsibility of this publication lies with the author. The European Union is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Any enquiries regarding this publication should be sent to us at:
Umut.Korkut@gcu.ac.uk

This document is available for download at <https://dradproject.com/>

Table of Contents

Acknowledgements	4
About the Project	5
Executive Summary/Abstract	6
1. Introduction	7
2. Methodology	7
2.1 Navigating the Evolution and Accessibility of the Map Interface	8
2.2 Option for Arabic Translation	11
3. Mapping Excellence: D9.3 Spatial Aspects of Deradicalisation	12
3.1. Florence (Italy)	13
3.1.1 Piazza Tasso (Florence).....	13
3.1.2 The “Anelli Mancanti” Association (Florence)	14
3.1.3 San Lorenzo (Florence).....	14
3.2. Helsinki (Finland)	15
3.2.1 Oodi (Helsinki)	15
3.2.2 Lapinlahden Lähde (Helsinki)	15
3.2.3 Maunula house (Helsinki).....	16
3.3. Prishtina (Kosovo)	18
3.3.1 Termokiss (Prishtina).....	18
3.3.2 The Bajram Kelmendi Street (Prishtina).....	19
3.3.3 The University of Prishtina Campus (Prishtina).....	21
3.4. Tbilisi (Georgia)	23
3.4.1 Deda Ena Park (Tbilisi)	23
3.4.2 Mzirui Park (Tbilisi).....	24
3.4.3 Former Hippodrome (Tbilisi)	26
3.5. Vienna (Austria)	27
3.5.1 Yppenplatz (Vienna)	27
3.5.2 Herderpark (Vienna).....	29
3.5.3 Wanda-Lanzer-Park (Vienna)	30
4. Bridging Academic and Public Realms through Interactive Visualization in Knowledge Dissemination	32

Acknowledgements

D.Rad express thanks and gratitude to the Map Design Team, including Dr. Ivo Furman, Dr. Alper Kirklar, Abdullah Alsharif, and Can Sucuoğlu. Their dedicated efforts have been instrumental in designing and developing our map webpage, as well as transforming the data from D.Rad Work Package 9 into a visual format. Special thanks are extended to all members of WP9 who contributed data for 9.3, enabling the conversion of the provided data into a visual representation.

About the Project

D.Rad is a comparative study of radicalisation and polarisation in Europe and beyond. It aims to identify the actors, networks, and wider social contexts driving radicalisation, particularly among young people in urban and peri-urban areas. D.Rad conceptualises this through the I-GAP spectrum (injustice-grievance-alienation-polarisation) with the goal of moving towards measurable evaluations of de-radicalisation programmes. Our intention is to identify the building blocks of radicalisation, which include a sense of being victimised; a sense of being thwarted or lacking agency in established legal and political structures; and coming under the influence of “us vs them” identity formulations.

D.Rad benefits from an exceptional breadth of backgrounds. The project spans national contexts including the UK, France, Italy, Germany, Poland, Hungary, Finland, Slovenia, Bosnia, Serbia, Kosovo, Israel, Iraq, Jordan, Turkey, Georgia, Austria, and several minority nationalisms. It bridges academic disciplines ranging from political science and cultural studies to social psychology and artificial intelligence. Dissemination methods include D.Rad labs, D.Rad hubs, policy papers, academic workshops, visual outputs and digital galleries. As such, D.Rad establishes a rigorous foundation to test practical interventions geared to prevention, inclusion and de-radicalisation.

With the possibility of capturing the trajectories of seventeen nations and several minority nations, the project will provide a unique evidence base for the comparative analysis of law and policy as nation states adapt to new security challenges. The process of mapping these varieties and their link to national contexts will be crucial in uncovering strengths and weaknesses in existing interventions. Furthermore, D.Rad accounts for the problem that processes of radicalisation often occur in circumstances that escape the control and scrutiny of traditional national frameworks of justice. The participation of AI professionals in modelling, analysing and devising solutions to online radicalisation will be central to the project’s aims.

Executive Summary/Abstract

In the digital age, emerging technologies empower marginalized perspectives to be shared online, transcending temporal and geographic boundaries. Accessible from the comfort of one's home, these platforms offer a space for diverse voices, provided access to the internet and appropriate technology. Digital and visual initiatives, showcasing creativity and community connectivity, present an opportunity for researchers to establish unique relationships with their audiences. This report delves into the creation process of the interactive map developed collaboratively with digital designers from Turkey, utilizing data from 16 countries.

The D.Rad interactive map, an innovative web application, serves as a visually appealing roadmap for exploring radical ideologies and deradicalisation interventions. Incorporating spatial aspects of deradicalisation and social inclusion-related arts and sports activities, this transformation of data enhances inclusivity, maximizing impact throughout the project's duration and beyond. The interactive visualizations within the D.Rad project shed light on radicalisation trends and best practices concerning human rights and deradicalisation.

The report details the main development of the D.Rad digital galleries, focusing on Deliverable D8.3. Initially conceived as separate visual repositories for Deliverables D9.3, D3.8, D4.4, D6.4, and D8.3, a strategic decision was made to consolidate them into one expansive, multidimensional interactive map. This approach enhances visual appeal, cost-effectiveness, and accessibility for a diverse audience, showcasing the correlation between D.Rad research work packages. Each deliverable's data is displayed independently within the unified map, preserving the integrity of individual research areas while emphasizing their interconnectedness.

Specifically, D9.3 contributes digital visualizations that represent the spatial aspects of deradicalisation efforts in Austria, Finland, Georgia, Kosovo, and Italy, adding a significant layer to the comprehensive findings of the entire project.

1. Introduction

To effectively engage with target audiences, the dissemination and exploitation objectives of a segment within Work Package 9 aimed to consolidate and develop the findings into a visual repository—an interactive digital map. D9.3 provides a concise summary and presents digital visualizations that highlight spatial aspects of deradicalisation efforts in Austria, Finland, Georgia, Kosovo, and Italy.

Interactive mapping employs digital imagery presented in map form, enabling functionalities such as zooming, panning, feature identification, report generation, and other ways of visualizing specific information on the map. This visual transformation of data enhances inclusivity across target audiences, maximizing impact not only during the project's duration but also in the post-project period. Within the D.Rad project, these interactive visualizations serve to illustrate trends in radicalisation and showcase best practices concerning human rights and deradicalisation.

To effectively disseminate the outcomes of a specific segment within Work Package 9 and capitalize on their impact, the project aimed to transform findings into an accessible and comprehensive visual repository—an interactive digital map. Documented in D9.3, this deliverable encapsulates a thorough summary and digital visualizations, presenting the spatial dimensions of deradicalisation initiatives in Austria, Finland, Georgia, Kosovo, and Italy.

Interactive mapping, as employed in this context, leverages digital imagery to create a dynamic map that facilitates functionalities like zooming, panning, feature identification, and report generation. This versatile approach allows users to engage with specific information, fostering a deeper understanding of the presented content. The transformation of data through this visual lens is strategic, aiming to foster inclusivity across diverse target audiences. By providing an interactive and visually compelling experience, the project seeks to maximize its impact not only during the project's lifecycle but also well into the future.

2. Methodology

Representatives from each country within the five national contexts collaborated to collect images and information that portray the spatial dimensions of deradicalisation efforts at selected D.Rad sites. This collaborative effort involved gathering photographs and textual details for each geographical site. Whenever feasible, researchers and D.Rad staff contributed their own photographs, specifically taken at site-specific locations. Subsequently, the textual information was organized and transformed into an Excel format. This step was taken to facilitate the work of map designers in the later stages of the project, ensuring a seamless integration of the

collected data into the interactive map. This collaborative process underscores the commitment to presenting a comprehensive and accurate depiction of spatial aspects related to deradicalisation efforts across the diverse D.Rad sites.

2.1 Navigating the Evolution and Accessibility of the Map Interface

Previous reports (3.8,4.4, 6.4,8.3) provide detailed accounts of the acquisition and evolution of the D.Rad map. By the time Deliverable 9.3 entered the developmental phase, the map had undergone various stages of refinement and had already been publicly accessible, incorporating data from Work Packages 3, 4, 6, and 8.

Visitors to the D.Rad website's landing page¹ will immediately recognize a prominently displayed tab labelled "Interactive Map" (see figure 1). Upon clicking or selecting this tab, users will be seamlessly directed to the dedicated map landing page (refer to figure 2).

Figure 1. D.Rad website landing page. Yellow arrow shows tab for D.Rad map

¹ <https://dradproject.com/>

Figure2 Interactive Map welcome page. The tab to the interactive map is highlighted above by the yellow arrow.

Upon reaching the welcome page of the map, seven tabs are prominently featured at the page's top. Users have the option to select the 'Map' tab, easily identifiable by a world globe icon, to access the interactive map (see figure 2). Once within the interactive map, users encounter a global map showcasing highlighted D.Rad countries. On the left-hand side, a list of all countries is presented (see figure 3).

Figure 3 List of D.Rad countries & an explanation of map content detailing the rationale behind the coloured buttons

The map contents' description offers valuable insights to aid users in understanding and navigating the interactive map. The description reads as follows:

The D.Rad interactive map serves as a visually engaging guide for those interested in exploring radicalisation and polarization in Europe and the Middle East. As of December 2023, multiple datasets are integrated into this map. Blue dots on the map indicate instances of radicalization, offering details about the event type and a summary. Pink dots represent stakeholders, their activities, and de-radicalization programs. Purple dots highlight select arts and sports-related social inclusion activities in Israel, Poland, Serbia, Slovenia, and the United Kingdom. Lastly, green dots signify spatial aspects of deradicalization efforts in Austria, Finland, Georgia, Kosovo, and Italy.

Visitors can select a D.Rad country. This option is available in the left-hand column of the map interface.

The various D.Rad work package activity are highlighted in various colours:

- **Blue** – Radical or Extremist Hot Spot Events (D3.8)
- **Pink** – State sponsored & NGO Deradicalisation programmes (D3.8)
- **Green** – Best Practice of arts and sports related social inclusion activities in selected D.Rad sites (D8.3)
- **Purple** - Spatial Aspects of Deradicalisation - Reclaiming Public Space - Interactive Map offers the empirical site-specific findings in consortium partners involved WP9 (D9.3)

Once countries are chosen, coloured buttons shift the viewers perspective across the categories highlighted above (Events - Deradicalisation programmes - Best practice arts & sports - Spatial Aspects of Deradicalisation). To navigate to purple or green dots (D8.3 / D9.3), viewers much first click the slide button from **blue** to **pink**. This will allow the full interface to switch to show 8.3 and 9.3 data.

2.2 Option for Arabic Translation

The D.Rad map offers users the convenient choice of accessing an Arabic translation. This language option is seamlessly integrated into the welcome page, providing a user-friendly experience for Arabic-speaking audiences (refer to figure 2).

As of now, the Arabic translation extends specifically to the welcome page, as depicted in figure 5. This strategic approach aims to enhance inclusivity and accessibility, ensuring that a broader audience, particularly those comfortable with

Arabic, can fully engage with the map's content. The commitment to linguistic diversity aligns with D.Rad's broader mission of fostering global engagement and understanding.

Figure 5. Welcome page translated to Arabic.

3. Mapping Excellence: D9.3 Spatial Aspects of Deradicalisation

D9.3 represents an innovative online map that has been meticulously crafted based on the empirical site-specific findings derived from the extensive research conducted in Work Package 9. The overarching goal of this endeavour is to leverage the power of visual representation to enhance the dissemination of information and broaden public outreach.

For every city included in the map, a comprehensive showcase of three best-practice examples of public spaces is presented. Each example is accompanied by detailed textual information, providing valuable insights into the unique approaches and initiatives implemented. Moreover, the inclusion of one or more pictures serves to visually capture the essence of these public spaces. In ensuring adherence to copyright regulations, all project partners were explicitly instructed to clarify the copyright status of the images. Partners were encouraged to either capture original photographs or provide appropriate references for sourced images.

Looking ahead, D.Rad aspires to further enrich the map by incorporating links to city reports. This strategic move is designed to empower interested visitors with the ability to delve deeper into each city's details, gaining a more comprehensive understanding of the specific findings and initiatives outlined in the map. By seamlessly connecting the online map to in-depth city reports, D.Rad aims to foster a richer and more immersive exploration of the multifaceted aspects of deradicalisation efforts across diverse urban landscapes.

3.1. Florence (Italy)

3.1.1 Piazza Tasso (Florence)

Description: This is the Piazza Tasso garden which located in the the San Frediano area. Piazza Tasso, with its sports grounds, benches, the “Pietro Thuar” city-library and the surrounding bars, is one of the most lively, multiethnic and inclusive space of the so called “Oltrarno” district, in the city center of Florence. It was cited by interview partners as a best-practice example because it plays a crucial role in maintaining the area ‘alive’. There are also a number of neighbourhood facilities such as the “Ardiglione” or “Nidiaci” park, a historic place behind the Carmine church (in which there is “ludoteca”, or a large room with toys and games where children play), a community canteen (*Bagni popolari*), accommodations for homeless people (*Albergo popolare*) and a community gym set up by “I Bianchi” organisation, which attracts many young adults, most of whom with a migration background.

Picture 1: Playground Piazza Tasso, © Andrea Gatti (University of Florence)

Picture 2: Piazza Tasso’s facilities: drinking fountains, © Andrea Gatti (University of Florence)

3.1.2 The “Anelli Mancanti” Association (Florence)

Description: The association “Anelli Mancanti” in via Palazzuolo (main train station area) is the most effective space as far as inclusion and (substantive) de-radicalisation are concerned. In Via Palazzuolo the concentration of more than 20 ethnic groups might well potentially give rise to a conflictual situation. The organization, offering language lessons, primarily to school children with a migration background, along with other cultural activities, let many of those migrants spend time together and become a reference point for many immigrant families.

Picture 1: Scuola Rucellai, Anelli Mancanti © www.anellimancanti.com

3.1.3 San Lorenzo (Florence)

Description: This is the Central Market of Florence, in San Lorenzo area. During the day, the streets are almost completely occupied by leather and clothing stalls in a crowded market (the vast majority of stalls belong to foreign people, such as Bangladeshi), but in the nighttime the streets are empty and lonely. In the San Lorenzo neighbourhood, residents and foreign communities act in an organised manner. Community labs and participatory meetings are often organized to discuss issues, addressed to social actors belonging to different institutions and aimed at promoting local inclusive practices and actions and at reaching a compromise about the implementation of some projects in the area.

Picture 1: San Lorenzo Central Market © Il Forchettiere

3.2. Helsinki (Finland)

3.2.1 Oodi (Helsinki)

Description: Oodi is Helsinki's central library, a three-floor multifunctional building inaugurated at the end of 2018 after a broad consultative planning process. The library is easily accessible, situated close to the railway station and the bus terminal. The library's policy is to be a free-of-charge indoor space for all residents irrespective of their age or background. Various activities are organised in Oodi, including programme for child families as well as band studios, sewing machines and 3D printers that the users can reserve. Organisations and residents can also use the space for their own events.

Picture 1: Oodi Library, © Joonas Hassinen (University of Helsinki)

3.2.2 Lapinlahden Lähde (Helsinki)

Description: Lapinlahden Lähde is a former mental hospital slightly outside Helsinki city centre. This place and its use have been subject to a heated political debate for decades. The space is currently run by mental health and arts organisations. Various cultural and mental health activities, both those free of charge and based on the work of volunteers as well as small-scale commercial services, are situated in the house. The space is open for the public, with mental health rehabilitators and artists among its users. The organisation running the space has also conducted projects to increase the inclusion of unemployed people and other vulnerable groups.

Picture 1: Lapinlahden Lähde, © Joonas Hassinen (University of Helsinki)

3.2.3 Maunula house (Helsinki)

Description: Maunula House is a multifunctional building which combines a library, a youth centre, an adult education centre, cultural events and café and acts as an important meeting point in the Maunula suburb in North Helsinki. The establishment of the house was the outcome of collaboration among various municipal units, residents, and the architect. This ethos of resident participation remains an integral part of the governance of the house. The steering team of the house includes representatives of the residents, and the users of the house are consulted when planning the activities of the house. Residents and associations can also organize own events in the premises.

Picture 1: Maunula House, © Emilia Palonen (University of Helsinki)

3.3. Prishtina (Kosovo)

3.3.1 Termokiss (Prishtina)

Description: What was originally intended to be the building serving as the base for the central heating factory of Prishtina, Termokos, has now been transformed into Termokiss, a vibrant social center that gathers Prishtina's youth, artists, and citizens from surrounding neighborhoods. It is an unfinished concrete structure that was constructed in 1997 by Termokos and is situated on a small plot of land owned by the Prishtina Municipality. It was established in 2016 as part of a joint effort from a group of young people, the Prishtina Architecture week and a foreign Swiss partner institute. Termokiss emerges as a compelling case in the context of inclusion and exclusion dynamics in public spaces due to its transformation over the years. Before it was turned into a social hub, it was associated with drug abuse and the area evoked fear among people from the surrounding neighborhoods, who avoided it. The reclaiming and revitalization of this area presents a compelling case of community-driven initiatives in challenging exclusionary dynamics and creating inclusive spaces that are embraced and utilized by people, regardless of their background or social status.

Picture 1: Entrance to the Termokiss building © Termokiss [Facebook page](#)

Picture 2: Indoor area at Termokiss © Termokiss [Facebook page](#)

Picture 3: A stray dog relaxing inside the premises of Termokiss © Termokiss [Facebook page](#)

3.3.2 The Bajram Kelmendi Street (Prishtina)

Description: The Bajram Kelmendi street is situated in the Vellusha neighbourhood of Prishtina. The neighbourhood got its name from the Vellusha river that once flowed through the city but was covered in the 1980s. The street underwent significant transformations in the past two decades. After the 1999 war in Kosovo, the area was swarmed with new residential buildings, which were largely built without permits or proper planning. Today, the Bajram Kelmendi Street has turned into a hub for the devout Muslim population of the city. The presence of the "4 Lullat" mosque, the premises of the Islamic Community of Kosovo, and the Faculty of Islamic Studies within close proximity has solidified the street's reputation as a hub for religious activities. The street is characterized by a vibrant array of shops and businesses

catering to the community's needs, including stores selling Islamic clothing, Halal food establishments, religious bookstores, etc. There are underlying lines of conflict that arise in the area due to the contrasting beliefs, values, and practices of different groups that reside in or frequent it.

Picture 1: The “4 Lullat” mosque at Bajram Kelmendi Street © [Añelo de la Krotsche \(Flickr\)](#)

Picture 2: A hijab store at Bajram Kelmendi Street © Nektar Zogiani ([Prishtina Insight](#))

3.3.3 The University of Prishtina Campus (Prishtina)

Description: The University of Prishtina Campus is situated in the heart of the city, serving as a vibrant hub of education and culture for its citizens. It encompasses various faculties of the University, whilst sitting amidst prominent architectural and cultural landmarks in the city, including the National Library of Kosovo, the National Gallery of Art and the Serbian Orthodox Church, the construction of which began during the 1990s amidst the backdrop of the Serbian occupation under Milosevic's regime. Up to this day the Church remains unfinished and non-functional and serves as a symbol of the unresolved conflict between Kosovo and Serbia. Within this space, various groups, including students, residents, business owners and passers-by coexist and interact. The campus area is thus a crucial space for knowledge exchange and artistic interactions in the city. It also serves as a space where contrasting versions of history and ethno-political tensions are manifested, most notably through the presence of the Orthodox Church, which is a site of collective memory for those who lived through the turbulent 1990s. It is a good example of how public space affects the shaping of particular identities.

Picture 1: The Serbian Orthodox Church © Donika Elshani (KCSS)

Picture 2: The National Library of Kosovo © Donika Elshani (KCSS)

Picture 3: Part of the University of Prishtina campus © Donika Elshani (KCSS)

3.4. Tbilisi (Georgia)

3.4.1 Deda Ena Park (Tbilisi)

Description: Deda Ena in Georgian means mother tongue. This public space acquired significant importance for locals in 1978 when hundreds of thousands of Georgians marched to protest the planned amendments in the Soviet constitution that would have stripped the Georgian language of the status of the sole state language. The Soviet government had to back down and withdraw the proposal. Later, the park where demonstrations started became known as Deda Ena (mother tongue) park, and a monument to the Georgian language was erected. As the Soviet Union was nearing its end in 1990, the 14th of April, in commemoration of that day, was declared the day of the mother tongue. In the late 2010s the park went through a major renovation which turned this public space into one of the attractions for tourists and youth. It also became the first public space in Tbilisi with a skateboard park.

Picture 1: Aerial view of the park © Tbilisi City Hall <https://tbilisi.gov.ge/news/11682>

Picture 2: The first ever skate park in Tbilisi in Deda Ena Park © Tbilisi City Hall <https://tbilisi.gov.ge/news/11682>

3.4.2 Mzirui Park (Tbilisi)

Description: Mzirui is a large park in the center of Tbilisi that was opened in 1982. The park was conceived as a space for children and is based on the characters from the Soviet Georgian writer Nodar Dumbadze. Similar to other public spaces in Tbilisi, Mziuri also suffered heavily in the 1990s due to the difficult social, economic, and political situation. However, this public space underwent extensive renovation in 2019-2020, turning it into a family-friendly green space in the middle of the city center. According to some of the experts interviewed for this project, it is one of the most inclusive public spaces in Tbilisi as everyone regardless of their age, social status, or gender can find something to do here.

Picture 1: Renovated Mzirui Park © Ministry of Regional Development and Infrastructure of Georgia
<https://www.facebook.com/mrdi.gov.ge/photos/a.3403996359633462/3403997956299969/>

Picture 2: Presentation of the renovated park to the local population by the Prime Minister © Ministry of Regional Development and Infrastructure of Georgia <https://www.facebook.com/mrdi.gov.ge/photos/a.3404594686240296/3404595836240181/>

Picture 3: Ducks in renovated Mziuri © Ministry of Regional Development and Infrastructure of Georgia <https://www.facebook.com/mrdi.gov.ge/photos/a.3403996359633462/3403996972966734/>

3.4.3 Former Hippodrome (Tbilisi)

Description: This public space is located between the two central districts of Tbilisi – Vake and Saburtalo. From 1948 until 2007 it served as a Hippodrome. In 2007, Hippodrome changed its location, while this particular space in the city center was privatized. In the late 2010s, the space was returned back to the City Hall and in 2020 the plan for turning the former Hippodrome into the Central Park was announced. Until the project is finished, it remains the public space that is used by people with various backgrounds and interests in the neighborhood. Side by side, this public space is used by Indian students for cricket games, rugby players, dog owners, or pensioners for their morning exercise. What needs to be noted is that while most of the public places follow the formal organization of space designed by the City Hall, the former Hippodrome is informally and naturally divided among the users of the space.

Picture 1: Former Tbilisi Hippodrome © Netgazeti.ge
<https://netgazeti.ge/news/487192/>

Picture 2: View of the former Hippodrome in 2020 © Tbilisi City Hall
<https://tbilisi.gov.ge/news/10736>

3.5. Vienna (Austria)

3.5.1 Yppenplatz (Vienna)

Description: Yppenplatz is located in the 16th district of Vienna and is connected to the longest street food market in all of Vienna. It consists of a square with several seating opportunities as well as a playground, a public toilet and sports facilities and is surrounded by the market and several cafes and bistros. It is a very vivid and popular public space that is used by different groups, a fact which is highlighted as a best-practice example for superdiversity by some, however, the space is also contested and an example of gentrification. There are frequent tensions due to the diverging interests of different user groups, noise and waste and several actors are present to mediate and accompany these conflicts.

Picture 1: Centre of Yppenplatz with football cage in the back © Miriam Haselbacher (ISR/ÖAW)

Picture 2: View from Yppenplatz towards the market © Miriam Haselbacher (ISR/ÖAW)

Picture 3: View of the street market © Miriam Haselbacher (ISR/ÖAW)

3.5.2 Herderpark (Vienna)

Description: Located in the 11th district of Vienna, this is one of the biggest parks of the district. It contains several activity zones, including playgrounds, a youth sports facility, a dog zone and a children's outdoor pool, which is free of charge. The park is surrounded by municipal residential buildings and is an example of social democratic urban planning. It was cited by interview partners as best-practice for two reasons: It is an example for participation processes and the proactive inclusion of citizens in urban renewal and young people were included in these participation processes, which is not always the case. In the case of Herderpark, a calisthenics facility was built at the request of young people. Staff members of Fairplayteam 11 (youth work) were in charge of polling the wishes of youth regarding urban spaces and there was the possibility to vote online on certain equipment.

Picture 1: Playground Herderpark © Josefa Stiegler (ISR/ÖAW)

Picture 2: Calisthenics facility Herderpark © Josefa Stiegler (ISR/ÖAW)

Picture 3: Soccer and basketball court Herderpark © Josefa Stiegler (ISR/ÖAW)

3.5.3 Wanda-Lanzer-Park (Vienna)

Description: This park is a typical example of a park in a densely built-up area with old residential buildings, where a part of a block was left vacant for a park. The possibilities are thus rather limited. The park was named by interview partners as a best-practice example of a redesign with the involvement of citizens. The cooperation between different actors was thereby described as being very good and involving a set of diverse actors. The City of Vienna is often criticized for leaving only very marginal decision-making competencies to citizens in urban participation processes. Consequently, solutions and best-practice examples are often rather small-scale, for which Wanda-Lanzer-park is a good example. Here, the redesign resulted in more greenery, including opportunities for urban gardening for residents, a new playground and a new lighting concept. However, the lack of green spaces and shading remains a problem.

Picture 1: Wanda-Lanzer-Park © Ursula Reeger (ISR/ÖAW)

Picture 2: Wanda-Lanzer-Park © Ursula Reeger (ISR/ÖAW)

4. Bridging Academic and Public Realms through Interactive Visualization in Knowledge Dissemination

(What can research practitioners learn from the D.Rad interactive Map?)

Interactive visualization tools, ranging from visual repositories to interactive maps, redefine how complex information is presented. Beyond being inclusive, these tools offer captivating and user-friendly experiences, dismantling the notion that academic research should be confined behind costly paywalls. The result is a more democratic and accessible dissemination of knowledge, allowing diverse segments of society to engage with and benefit from scholarly insights. As societal engagement in research grows, these visualization tools become conduits for academics to freely share their knowledge across social and geographical boundaries. This sharing of knowledge not only narrows the gap between academic experts and community-based forums² but also transcends social borders, reaching communities at their core. The impact of disseminating knowledge through interactive visualization extends beyond accessibility. It introduces innovative methods to actively involve audiences who might remain elusive through traditional communication channels. By portraying digital geographies of (de)radicalisation visually, this approach not only informs but also sparks interest, understanding, and collaboration within diverse communities.

In essence, the landscape of knowledge dissemination has evolved, and interactive visualisation stands at its forefront. Acting as a bridge between academic and public spheres, it transforms how information is shared, consumed, and engaged with, shaping a more collaborative and informed society.

² Lassiter, Luke Eric. 2005. *The Chicago Guide to Collaborative Ethnography*. Chicago, London: University of Chicago Press.